

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF TENSILE BEHAVIOR OF CARALL FABRICATED WITH DIFFERENT FIBER ORIENTATION

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ABSTRACT

Fiber metal laminates (FMLs) are advanced lightweight thin structural composite materials, used in aerospace industry, prepared with alternate layers of metal sheet and fiber reinforced polymer composite. In the present work, the carbon fiber aluminum laminates (CARALLs) were fabricated using AA2024-T3 of and carbon fiber epoxy prepreg in 3/2 layup sequence with aluminum at top and bottom side. The laminates were fabricated in three different configurations i.e. Al/0°/Al/0°/Al, Al/90°/Al/0°/Al, Al/90°/Al/90°/Al and referred as CARALL – 1, CARALL – 2 and CARALL – 3. The effect of fiber orientation on tensile strength was investigated by uniaxial tensile testing at cross head speed of 1 mm/min. Finite element (FE) simulation using ABAQUS/Explicit was also performed for all the cases in order to compare the stress development and to appraise the progressive damage under tensile loading. For simulation, the meso-level modeling approach was used to define the properties of individual constituent of FMLs. The predicted FE results reveal that Mises stress generated on carbon fiber at 0° are much higher than aluminum sheet at a same time step in the CARALL – 1 whereas the stress generated in carbon fiber at 90° is lower than aluminum sheet in the CARALL – 2 and CARALL – 3. The comparison of FE predicted tensile stress of three different FMLs are aligned with experimental observations. Highest value of ultimate tensile strength can be noted in the CARALL – 1 whereas the minimum is observed in CARALL – 3. It is noted that in CARALL – 1 and CARALL – 2 fracture of fiber initiates the damage followed by interfacial delamination and fracture of aluminum, while in CARALL – 3 failure is controlled by fracture of aluminum.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lightweight metal alloys such as aluminum, magnesium, and titanium are extensively utilized in multiple industrial applications for instance in aircraft industry. On the other hand, the monolithic metal alloys have less ability to resist crack growth under fatigue loading. To overcome this issue, many researchers and scientists utilized fiber reinforced polymer (FRPs) composites that have good strength to weight ratio, fatigue strength, corrosion resistance etc. as compared to metals and their alloys [1-2]. However, the FRPs have low impact resistance, less interfacial strength and tendency to fail catastrophically [3]. Recently, fiber metal laminates (FMLs) were fabricated as a new category of hybrid composites that incorporates the better mechanical properties as reported by many researchers such as impact resistance, fatigue strength, damage tolerance and open hole tensile strength in comparison to monolithic metal alloys and FRPs under different loading condition [4-5]. The presence of metallic layer, prepreg and interface in a one system makes challenging task to predict the mechanical behavior and failure of fiber metal laminates. Many researchers investigated the mechanical behavior of FMLs experimentally and numerically.

Carillo et al. [6] studied the FMLs that consists of aluminum and glass fiber reinforced propylene layers as a distinct constituent in four different stacking sequence during tensile loading. The results of tensile loading revealed that the stress-strain diagram was linear till the maximum load and then rapid drop in load had been encountered. Torshizi et al. [7] investigated the effect of fiber orientation angle on tensile behavior in FMLs that incorporates glass fiber and kevlar fiber together with aluminum sheet experimentally, analytically and numerically. They observed that the laminates

in zero fiber orientation angle have been shown maximum elastic modulus, yield strength, and ultimate tensile strength. Lee et al.[8] also conducted an experimental, numerical and analytical study to evaluate and observe deformation/damage behavior under tensile loading in FMLs based on self-reinforced polypropylene. The analytical study was conducted by the utilizing rule of mixture and classical laminate theory. They found that the stress-strain curve predicted through analytical and numerical model were in good agreement with experimental results. Sharma et al. [9] investigated the tensile strength of glass fiber reinforced aluminum laminates with varying the thickness of the aluminum sheet and keeping metal volume fraction constant experimentally. They also developed the finite element simulation and evaluate the strain field by Digital Image Correlation. Few resreachers studied about impact strength of carbon fiber aluminum laminate (CARALL) and compared with glass fiber aluminum laminate (GLARE) and other laminates [10-11]. They observed that CARALL have better impact resistance than their GLARE and other fiber metal laminates.

In the present work, the tensile behavior of fabricated carabon fiber aluminum laminates in different configuration were studied experimentally. The Finite Element (FE) modelling with cohesive elements at the interface was conducted to examine progressive failure behavior of CARALLs and variation of stress along the the thickness direction. The stress-displacement curves of different CARALLs obtained from experiments were compared with FE simulated analysis.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials and manufacturing technique

To fabricate fiber metal laminates (FMLs), the aluminum alloys are generally used due to their extensive application in many industries such as aircraft, automotive etc. In this work, an AA2024-T3 of thickness (0.3 mm) containing Cu (3.80-4.90 %), Mg (1.20-1.80 %), Si (0-0.50 %), Cr (0-0.1 %), Zn (0-0.25 %), Mn (0.3-0.9 %) were used as metal layer and procured commercially from the vendors in tampered (T3) condition. The carbon fiber prepreg (305 GSM) comprises of 62 % fiber and impregnated with epoxy (UF – 3325) were used as reinforcement and procured from Fiberglast Development Corporation, Ohio, USA.

Figure 1: Schematic of FML showing stacking sequence for (a) CARALL – 1 (b) CARALL – 2 and (c) CARALL – 3.

The FMLs of approximate same thickness were fabricated in three different configurations as shown in Figure 1 (Al/0°/Al/0°/Al, Al/90°/Al/0°/Al, Al/90°/Al/90°/Al) and referred as CARALL – 1, CARALL – 2 and CARALL – 3 as shown in Table 1. The aluminum sheets were initially snipped into 250 mm × 100 mm size. After that aluminum sheets were cleaned to remove the dirt particles, oil, grease etc. by MEK (Methyl Ethyl Ketone) and chromic acid anodized (CAA). The anodizing was conducted in the chromium (VI) oxide in the electrolytic solution at 20 V for 40 minutes to get the desired surface for adhesion. The alkaline etching (10 wt% NaOH in ultrapure water) and acid etching (15 vol% HNO₃ in ultrapure water) were conducted prior to anodizing to remove residual stress present on cleaned surface. The aluminum sheet and carbon fiber prepreg were hand layup in the desired sequence as shown in the Table 1 and placed in the mold cavity. Thereafter, the mold was closed and cured at 120 °C with 5 °/min heating rate for 2 hours in the compression molding machine applying 2 MPa pressure.

FML code	Configuration	Total Thickness (mm)
CARALL – 1	Al/0°/Al/0°/Al	1.5
CARALL – 2	Al/90°/Al/0°/Al	1.5
CARALL – 3	Al/90°/Al/90°/Al	1.5

Table 1: Details of fabricated carbon fiber aluminum laminate in different configuration.

2.2 Uni- axial tensile test

The uni axial tensile test were conducted in all the three configuration in the Zwick Roell (Z50) universal testing machine in ambient condition. The dimensions and geometry of tested specimen were prepared according to ASTM 3039 [12] as shown in Figure 2. No tabs were used in the gripped section during testing. The cross head speed during the test was 1 mm/min. Two trials were conducted for each configuration.

Figure 2: Schematic and dimension of FMLs for tensile test of (a) CARALL – 1 (b) CARALL – 2 and (c) CARALL – 3.

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

The fiber metal laminates are generally modeled by using three techniques namely Micro-level, Meso-level and Macro-level [13]. In micro-level modeling, all the components (matrix, fiber, metal sheet) of

laminates are analyzed distinctly. In meso-level study, each layer and their interaction with an adjacent layer in the laminate are modeled and analyzed individually. The entire laminate is modeled as a homogenized laminate in the macro-level study. In the present study, the meso-level modeling approach was utilized in this study to numerically analyze the FMLs in the ABAQUS/Explicit finite element software in three different configurations under tensile loading. As the individual constituent (aluminum sheet and carbon fiber epoxy prepreg) used in the laminates exhibits distinct mechanical properties therefore, the different constitutive models were used to define the mechanical behavior.

3.1 Model and damage criterion for aluminum alloys

Aluminum alloys were modeled as an elasto-plastic material using Johnson- Cook flow stress equation as expressed in equation (1) [14].

$$\sigma = [A + B (\bar{\epsilon}_{pl})^n] \left[1 + C \ln \left(\frac{\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}_{pl}}{\bar{\epsilon}_0} \right) \right] [T^{*m}] \quad (1)$$

Where A , B , and C are material parameters, $\bar{\epsilon}_{pl}$ is the equivalent plastic strain, $\frac{\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}_{pl}}{\bar{\epsilon}_0}$ is the dimensionless plastic strain rate, n and m are material constants. The value of T^* (homologous temperature) is assumed to be one because the temperature was kept constant in the entire analysis. To model onset damage in the aluminum alloy sheet, ductile damage criterion was used. In this model, the equivalent plastic strain at damage is assumed to be function of stress triaxiality and strain rate. The elastic properties (Elastic modulus (E) = 73100 MPa, Poisson's ratio (ν) = 0.33) of AA2024-T3 were taken from material data sheet. The material parameters and properties for AA 2024-T3 is shown in Table 2.

Johnson Cook parameters	$A = 368$ MPa, $B = 683$ MPa, $C = 0.0083$, $m = 1.7$, $n = 0.79$
Damage initiation properties	Fracture strain = 0.18, Stress triaxiality = 0.33

Table 2: Material parameters and properties for AA2024-T3 [15]

3.2 Model and damage criterion for carbon fiber reinforced epoxy polymer composites (CFRP)

The CFRP prepreg layer was modeled as transversely isotropic material and their properties were described in Table 3. To define damage initiation in the prepreg layer Hashin 2D criterion based on plane stress condition was used separately [16]. The Hashin 2D criterion includes different damage behaviors such as fiber tension, fiber compression, matrix tension, and matrix compression. These failure initiation criterion can be expressed as given below in equation (2) to (5).

Layer properties [17]	$E_{11} = 132$ GPa, $E_{22} = 10.3$ GPa, $E_{33} = 10.3$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.25$, $\nu_{31} = 0.25$, $\nu_{23} = 0.38$, $G_{12} = 6.5$ GPa, $G_{13} = 6.5$ GPa, $G_{23} = 3.91$ GPa, $X_T = 2100$ MPa, $X_C = 1050$ MPa, $Y_T = 24$ MPa, $Y_C = 132$ MPa, $S_{12} = 75$ MPa
Fracture energies [18]	$G_{1t} = 40$ KJ/m ² , $G_{1c} = 40$ KJ/m ² , $G_{2t} = 0.25$ KJ/m ² , $G_{2c} = 0.75$ KJ/m ²

Table 3: Material parameters and properties for carbon fiber prepreg

Fiber tension

$$R_{ft} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T} \right)^2 + \alpha \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{S_{12}^2} \right) = \begin{cases} \geq & 1 \text{ failure} \\ < & 1 \text{ no failure} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Fiber compression

$$R_{fc} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C} \right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1 & \text{failure} \\ < 1 & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Matrix tension

$$R_{mt} = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 = \begin{cases} \geq 1 & \text{failure} \\ < 1 & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Matrix compression

$$R_{mc} = \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_{23}} \right)^2 - 1 \right] \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_C} \right)^2 + \frac{(\sigma_{22})^2}{4S_{23}^2} + \frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{S_{12}^2} = \begin{cases} \geq 1 & \text{failure} \\ < 1 & \text{no failure} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Here, σ_{ij} indicates the stress components in the material direction. X_T , Y_T indicates the allowable tensile strength in fiber and matrix respectively. Similarly, X_C , Y_C represents allowable compressive stress in fiber and matrix. S_{23} , S_{12} denote the allowable shear strength along two principal material direction. When the damage initiation conditions (equation (2) to (5)) fulfilled, the stiffness of material degraded with a further increase in load. Therefore, it is required to evaluate the damage variable at each incremental displacement. The detailed method used for quantification of damage variable is discussed in reference [19]. However, the fundamental equation used for evaluation of damaged elasticity matrix was mentioned in equation (6) in this work that is already integrated with ABAQUS.

$$[C_d] = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1 - d_f)E_{11} & (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)\nu_{21}E_{11} & 0 \\ (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)\nu_{12}E_{22} & (1 - d_m)E_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1 - d_s)DG_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$D = 1 - (1 - d_f)(1 - d_m)\nu_{12}\nu_{21} \quad (7)$$

In the equation 6 and 7, d_f , d_m and d_s are the damage variables of fiber damage, matrix damage and shear damage respectively.

3.3 Traction – relative displacement law

The uncoupled traction separation law as mentioned in equation 8 is utilized to specify cohesive interaction between two adjacent layers in the laminate.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} t_n \\ t_s \\ t_t \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{nn} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_{ss} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_{tt} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \delta_n \\ \delta_s \\ \delta_t \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Where t_n is the out of plane normal stress and t_s and t_t are out of plane transverse shear stresses. δ_n , δ_s , δ_t and K_{nn} , K_{ss} , K_{tt} are the corresponding displacements and penalty stiffness along the normal and transverse direction. Delamination often occurred, when any of the traction components exceeds the allowable stress in the different structure under mixed mode loading. To model onset delamination in this work the quadratic nominal stress approach as mentioned in equation 9 were used.

$$\left\{ \frac{t_n}{t_n^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_s}{t_s^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{t_t}{t_t^0} \right\}^2 = 1 \quad (9)$$

3.4 Discretization of finite element model

The explicit time integration approach was utilized with the help of ABAQUS/ Explicit module to avoid convergence and high time consumption issue encountered during implicit solutions. Although the specimen has geometric and loading symmetry, the full-length specimen was modeled to observe progressive damage failure. One end of the specimen was placed stationary and the displacement was applied to another end of the specimen (Figure 3) as done during the experiment in the uniaxial tensile test. Similarly, the gripped region was encastred by confining all six degree of freedoms, $U_1 = U_2 = U_3 = UR_1 = UR_2 = UR_3 = 0$ and the displacement is applied along longitudinal axis (x axis) in the other gripped region as shown in Figure 3. The eight node continuum shell elements (SC8R) and the eight node solid brick element (C3D8R) were used to model the composite layer and aluminum sheet respectively. The mesh sensitivity analysis is conducted to improve the accuracy of solution. On the basis of this analysis, the element size of $0.4 \text{ mm} \times 0.4 \text{ mm} \times 0.15 \text{ mm}$ and $0.8 \text{ mm} \times 0.4 \text{ mm} \times 0.15 \text{ mm}$ were used in gauge section and gripping section respectively in each FML's. The surface based interaction is used in this work to define the contact between composite layer and aluminum. The friction coefficient between the aluminum and composite layer is assumed to be 0.3.

Figure 3: (a) Applied boundary condition (b) mesh for tensile test of all CARALLs.

4 RESULTS AND DISSCUSSION

4.1 Stress- displacement response of AA2024-T3 and CARALLs

The experimental stress- displacement response for AA2024-T3 are shown in Figure 4. The experimental and FE simulated stress-displacement behavior of CARALLs during tensile test are shown in Figure 5(a) and 5(b).

Figure 4: Experimental stress-displacement curve for AA2024-T3.

The experimental tensile properties obtained from Figure 4 and 5(a) are shown in Table 4. It is clear from the Figure 5(a) and Figure 5(b) that the simulated stress-displacement behaviors are in good agreement with experimental results in case of CARALLs. However, the ultimates stress generated in CARALLs during simulation are more due to the material properties of individual constituent of CARALLs. The tensile stress is increasing till maximum load then sudden drop occurs in CARALL – 1 as shown in Figure 5(b). This sudden drop is may be due to the delamination or local fiber failure occurs in the laminate. It is depicted from FE simulation as shown in Figure 6 (a) that the delamination and local fiber occurs simultaneously after attaining peak load condition in CARALL – 1. After sudden drop, the majority of load was carried by aluminum alloy sheet and ultimate failure occurs at fracture strain of individual component.

Figure 5: (a) Experimental and (b) FE simulated stress-displacement curve for CARALL – 1, CARALL – 2 and CARALL – 3.

Figure 6: FE simulated response just after reaching ultimate tensile strength in (a) CARALL – 1 (b) CARALL – 2.

	AA2024-T3	CARALL – 1	CARALL – 2	CARALL – 3
Ultimate tensile stress (MPa)	394.82	971.04	513.97	248.34
Displacement at failure (mm)	11.67	18.54	17.95	19.19

Table 4: Experimental results of CARALLs under tensile loading.

The stress generated in the laminate CARALL – 2 is increasing till maximum load applied similar to the CARALL – 1 but the ultimate stress produced are less compared to CARALL – 1. The percentage of sudden drop in tensile strength is also lesser than CARALL – 1 due to the delamination and local fiber fracture occurs only the layer that was oriented in the loading direction as predicted by FE simulation shown in Figure 6. However, no delamination and fiber failure are observed in the layer that was oriented transverse to the loading direction in FE simulation. However, the ultimate fracture of CARALL – 2 occurs due to fracture strain of aluminum sheet. Moreover, the stress displacement behavior for CARALL – 3 is similar to AA2024-T3 due to the fiber is oriented transverse to the applied load.

Figure 7: Variation of FE predicted Mises stress along the thickness direction in (a) CARALL – 1 (b) CARALL – 2 and (c) CARALL – 3 at different time steps. (Note: I represents AA2024-T3 and II represents carbon fiber prepreg layer)

Figure 8: Cross sectional views of laminates after experimental uniaxial tensile test in (a) CARALL – 1 (b) CARALL – 2 and (c) CARALL – 3.

Figure 9: FE predicted failure pattern of laminates after tensile test in (a) CARALL – 1 (b) CARALL – 2 and (c) CARALL – 3.

The variation of Mises stress as predicted from FE simulation along the thickness direction for all the three CARALLs at different time step till initiation of failure in the laminates are shown in

Figure 7. It can be predicted from the numerical results as shown in Figure 7(a) that the stress generated at the aluminum alloy layer of the laminates are lesser comparison to the stress generated in the prepreg in which the carbon fiber is oriented in 0° at any particular time step in the CARALL – 1 configurations. This is mainly due to the higher stiffness of carbon fiber along 0° orientation. The variation of Mises along the thickness direction in CARALL – 2 are shown in Figure 7(b). It can be observed that the Mises stress are maximum in carbon fiber that are aligned along the direction of loading and minimum in the carbon fiber layer that are aligned transverse to the loading direction till failure initiation.

The experimental and FE simulated fractured images of carbon fiber aluminium laminates after tensile test are shown in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9. It can be observed from Figure 8(a) and Figure 9(a) that the delamination at the interphase and fiber pull out are the two fracture mechanism in CARALL – 1 in the tensile test. Further, the local fiber fracture and delamination are observed only at position wher fibers oriented along the direction of loading as shown in Figure 8(b) and 9(b) in CARALL – 2. The matrix cracking or fiber splitting as shown in Figure 8(c) and 9(c) is observed as major failure mechanism in CARALL – 3.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The experimental and FE simulated tensile behaviour of three fabricated CARALLs are presented in this work. The the stress-displacement behaviour of the CARALLs obtained from uniaxial tensile experiments are in good agreement with FE simulated tensile behaviour of CARALLs. Tesile results of CARALLs revealed that the tensile strength and failure mechanism are mainly depends on the orientation of fiber with respect to the rolling direction of aluminium or direction of applied load. Maximum ultimate tensile strength is obtained in CARALL – 1 while minimum in CARALL – 3. Approximately 250 % increase in ultimate tensile strength is observed in CARALL – 1 as compared to the AA2024-T3. The Mises stress varies along the thickness direction at a particular time step in each laminates. Delamination and fiber fracture is domainant failure mechanism in CARALL – 1 and CARALL – 2. However, fiber splitting (matrix cracking) is major failure mechanism in CARALL – 3.

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